

"Zero Trust Security in the Modern Workforce: A 2025 Guide to Enhanced Cyber Resilience"

Author: Seyed Farzad Mirmiran¹, Business & Academic Researcher, CEU university; DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14031937

Executive Summary:

As cyber threats grow in scale and sophistication, traditional perimeter-based security models are no longer sufficient for modern, hybrid workplaces. With more employees accessing company resources remotely, a **Zero Trust Security** approach has emerged as an essential strategy to safeguard sensitive data and systems. This white paper explores the foundations of Zero Trust, its critical role in today's workforce, and actionable steps for implementing a Zero Trust model to ensure organizational security and compliance in 2025.

Dr. Mirmiran Publications

¹ - Senior Academic & Business Researcher at CEU University;
([Dr.Seyed Farzad Mirmiran \(gumroad.com\)](mailto:Dr.Seyed.Farzad.Mirmiran@gumroad.com)) or;
<https://drmirmiran.gumroad.com/> & drmirmiran@yahoo.com)